

Constitutive modeling of plastically deformed and damaged bamboo under monotonic increasing uniaxial compressive load and cyclic uniaxial compressive load using the principles of continuum damage mechanics and the theory of endochronic plasticity

Fozao D.S.¹ et Foudjet A.E.²

(1) **Etablissement** : Ministry of Public Works, Yaoundé, Cameroon / e-mail : zaoden@hotmail.com

(2) **Superviseur Académique** : Professeur Titulaire des Universités, CRESA Forêt-Bois, Faculté d'Agronomie et des Sciences Agricoles, Université de Dschang, Cameroun

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1. General objective

The general objective of this work is to study the behaviour of bamboo culms under the monotonic increasing and cyclic uniaxial compressive loading regimes.

2. Specific objectives

- To carry out laboratory tests on the bamboo species *Oxytenanthera abyssinica*, found in the Congo Basin Rain Forest, using the monotonic and cyclic uniaxial compressive loading regimes.
- To determine the constitutive relationship of damaged bamboo under these loading regimes.
- To compare the stress-strain curves of the test specimens of bamboo culms produce from the test data and those produced using the constitutive relationships developed.

3. Problem Statement and Research Hypotheses

Bamboo is an example of an engineering material that can be used to build structures in adverse situations such as under wind loads and in earthquake prone areas. Bamboo culms contain micro cracks which result from natural factors such as wind loads and environmental climatic changes.

With the advances in technology and for economic reasons, the inelastic behaviour of engineering materials must be taken into consideration when designing engineering structures to resist very heavy loads.

Although some amount of effort has been directed at determining the characteristics of bamboo, very little has been done on the study of its behaviour under loading. No mathematical models exist that can be used to model its behaviour under monotonic as well as cyclic uniaxial compressive loading.

Therefore, the hypothesis of this research work is that: “the behaviour of cracked bamboo subjected to monotonic uniaxial compressive loading or cyclic uniaxial compressive loading beyond its elastic limit can be predicted using analytical formulations”.

4. Statement of Originality

Bamboo can be used as an alternative material in the construction industry to replace timber. It is a material that has a very high strength to mass ratio and has so many advantages as compared to timber. The use of bamboo is however conditioned to the fact that adequate information on its characteristics and a satisfactory modeling of its behaviour under loading is required to facilitate its use as a construction material.

An experimental investigation and a mathematical modeling of the behaviour of the bamboo species *Oxytenanthera abyssinica*, under monotonic as well as cyclic uniaxial compressive loadings are performed in this study. Several samples of this bamboo species were tested to collect the necessary data for this study. In this research work, three mathematical models are proposed to study the behaviour of bamboo under monotonic uniaxial compression loading and other models are proposed to study the unloading and reloading curves of the cyclic behaviour of bamboo.

This study is quite new and the following new concepts have been developed:

1. The coupling of the endochronic theory of plasticity with continuum damage mechanics, to study of the behaviour of bamboo under monotonic uniaxial compressive loading.
2. The existence of the envelope curves and the shakedown limits in the cyclic behaviour of bamboo.

3. Modeling of the unloading and reloading curves for bamboo under cyclic uniaxial compressive loads.

5. Material and methods

5.1. Equipment and Materials used

The equipment used included :

A hark saw, sand paper, a vernier caliper (manual version), a measuring tape, an electronic balance (the Scaltec mark), an oven (mark Heraeus), a bucket, the universal press measuring up to 2000kN, the CBR testing machine (LABOTEST) measuring up to 50kN equipped with a micrometer. A computer equipped with the EXCEL software, to treat the data, was also used.

The materials used are *Bambusa vulgaris* and *Oxytenantera abyssinica*, two species of bamboo found in the Congo Basin Rain Forest, water, and cement. The bamboo specimens were tested at varied moisture contents, some of the samples were oven dried; others were soaked in water and others air dried.

5.2. Testing Procedure

The preparation and testing of the materials were carried out in the Metallic workshop and the Civil Engineering Laboratory of the National Advanced School of Public Works Yaounde. For the cyclic tests, several cycles of unloading and reloading were performed on the materials and for the monotonic loading, the samples were loaded continuously until complete failure.

5.3. Presentation of the Tests Results

The tests results are presented in the form of failure mechanisms and graphs showing the relations between the stresses and strains. The stresses and the strains were calculated, using the original sample dimensions, from the loads applied and the deformations produced. Some of the graphs from the tests results are shown in figures 2a to 2c below.

6. Mathematical Modeling of the Behaviour of Bamboo

The behaviour of bamboo under uniaxial compressive loading is non-linear and this non-linear behaviour may be attributed to two distinct mechanical processes, which are plasticity and damage. These two degradation phenomena are best described by the theories of plasticity and continuum damage mechanics.

Consequently, the use of the continuum damage mechanics framework associated with the combined use of the elastic-plastic constitutive equations is vital

to better describe the behaviour of bamboo subjected to monotonic uniaxial compressive loading.

In this research work, three mathematical models named Fozao-Foudjet 1, Fozao-Foudjet 2 and Fozao-Foudjet 3, have been developed and proposed by us to study the behaviour of bamboo under the monotonic uniaxial compressive loading regime.

6.1. Developing the Expression Fozao-Foudjet 1

The first model, Fozao-Foudjet 1, is based on the coupling of the theory of plasticity using the endochronic theory of plasticity developed by Valanis, K. C., in 1971 and the principles of isotropic damage developed by Kachanov in 1958, with the strain equivalence principle. This model is given as follows:

$$\sigma = \begin{cases} E_0 \varepsilon & \text{for } \varepsilon \leq \varepsilon_0 \\ A_0 (1 + \beta_1 \varepsilon) \left[1 - \frac{1}{(1 + \beta_1 \varepsilon)^{n_1}} \right] (e^{-\gamma(\varepsilon - \varepsilon_0)}) & \text{for } \varepsilon \geq \varepsilon_0 \end{cases} \quad \text{(Eq. 1)}$$

$$A_0 = E_0 \varepsilon_0 \left[\frac{(1 + \beta_0 \varepsilon_0)^{(n_1 - 1)}}{(1 + \beta_0 \varepsilon_0)^{n_1} - 1} \right] \quad \text{(Eq. 2)}$$

$$\beta_0 = k\beta \text{ and } n_1 = 1 + \frac{\delta}{\beta} \quad \text{(Eq. 3)}$$

$$\beta_1 = \frac{\beta_0}{\alpha} \quad \text{(Eq. 4)}$$

In the mathematical expressions given above, k, δ , are constants used in the endochronic theory of plasticity while E_0 is the modulus of elasticity of the undamaged material and β is the softening or hardening coefficient. Since bamboo is a material with softening behaviour, the value of β is negative.

6.2. Developing Expression Fozao-Foudjet 2

The second model, Fozao-Foudjet 2, was developed by adapting the models produced by Mazars and Pijaudier-Cabot to study the behaviour of concrete under monotonic uniaxial compressive loading. The mathematical model proposed is given as:

$$\sigma = (k_0)^{\lambda_1} (1 - \varphi) E_0 \varepsilon \quad \text{(Eq. 5)}$$

$$\text{Where } \varphi = 1 - \frac{\varepsilon_0}{\varepsilon} (1 - B) - B e^{\left(\frac{\varepsilon_0 - \varepsilon}{\varepsilon_c} \right)} \quad \text{(Eq. 6)}$$

$$\text{and } B = \frac{[\sigma_{c \max} - E_0 \varepsilon_0]}{E_0 \varepsilon_0 \left[(k_0)^{\lambda_0} e^{\left(\frac{\varepsilon_0 - \varepsilon_c}{\varepsilon_c} \right)} - 1 \right]} \quad \text{(Eq. 7)}$$

The values of the constants λ_0 and λ_1 vary respectively as $1.00 \leq \lambda_0 \leq 1.38$ and $0.0 \leq \lambda_1 \leq 0.13$.

When $\lambda_0 = 0.00$ and $\lambda_1 = 1.00$, the model Fozao-Foudjet 2 becomes exactly the same as the model proposed by Mazars and Pijaudier Cabot to study the behaviour of concrete.

Figure 1: Monotonic Stress-Strain Curve of Bamboo used to develop Fozao-Foudjet 3 from the Smith and Young's expression

6.3. Developing Expression Fozao-Foudjet 3

The third mathematical model was developed from the model produced by Smith and Young to study the behaviour of concrete under monotonic uniaxial compressive loading, by using the monotonic compressive Stress-Strain Curve shown in figure 1 below. The new point A with coordinates (ϵ_a, σ_a) is included to define the softening (or descending) branch of the curve.

The third model Fozao-Foudjet 3 is given as:

$$\sigma = \begin{cases} E_0 \epsilon & \text{for } \epsilon \leq \epsilon_0 \\ \lambda_2 Q + D^{\lambda_3} \sigma_{c \max} k_c e^{(1-k_c) \epsilon} & \text{for } \epsilon > \epsilon_0 \end{cases} \quad \text{(Eq. 8)}$$

Where the constants Q and D, determined using the points (ϵ_a, σ_a) and $(\epsilon_c, \sigma_{c \max})$ from the graph of figure 1 are given as:

$$Q = \frac{(\sigma_a - \sigma_{c \max} k_a e^{(1-k_a) \epsilon_a})}{(1 - k_a e^{(1-k_a) \epsilon_a})} \quad \text{(Eq. 9)}$$

and

$$D = \frac{(\sigma_{c \max} - \sigma_a)}{(1 - k_a e^{(1-k_a) \epsilon_a}) \sigma_{c \max}} \quad \text{(Eq. 10)}$$

While $k_c = \frac{\epsilon}{\epsilon_c}$ and $k_a = \frac{\epsilon_a}{\epsilon_c}$ (Eq. 11)

The values of λ_2 and λ_3 vary as $0.0 \leq \lambda_2$ and $0.0 \leq \lambda_3 \leq 1.16$. When $\lambda_2=0.0$ and $\lambda_3=0.0$, this model becomes exactly the same as that proposed to study the behavior of concrete.

6.5 Modeling of the Cyclic Behaviour of Bamboo

Expressions used to study the behaviour of concrete under cyclic compressive loading were adapted and

proposed to study the behaviour of bamboo under this loading regime. Two empirical relations were proposed to idealize the unloading paths of the cyclic behaviour of bamboo. These are an exponential type function and a power type function of order n.

The exponential type equation is given in equation 12.

$$\sigma = B_1 e^{(C_1 \beta_1 \lambda)} E_0 (\epsilon - \epsilon_{pl}) \quad \text{(Eq. 12)}$$

$$B_1 = \left(\frac{r_1 (1 - \phi_{un})}{r_1 - 1} \right) \quad \text{(Eq. 13)}$$

$$C_1 = \text{Log} \left(\frac{R_1 (1 - \phi_{un}) (r_1 - 1)}{r_1} \right) \quad \text{(Eq. 14)}$$

$$\beta_1 = \left(1 - \frac{(\epsilon - \epsilon_{pl})}{(\epsilon_{un,(n)} - \epsilon_{pl})} \right) \quad \text{(Eq. 15)}$$

$$r_1 = \frac{\epsilon_{un,(n)}}{\epsilon_{pl}} \quad \text{(Eq. 16)}$$

$$R_1 = \frac{E_{pl}}{E_0} \quad \text{(Eq. 17)}$$

The expression for the power type equation is given in equation (18) that follows.

$$\sigma = \left(\frac{(1 - \bar{\epsilon})}{(1 + \alpha_0 \bar{\epsilon})} \right)^{\alpha_0} \sigma_{un} \quad \text{(Eq. 18)}$$

Where

$$\alpha_0 = 1 + \left(\frac{\epsilon_{pl}}{\epsilon_{un}} \right)^\kappa \quad \text{(Eq. 19)}$$

$$\bar{\epsilon} = \frac{(\epsilon - \epsilon_{un,(n)})}{(\epsilon_{pl} - \epsilon_{un,(n)})} \quad \text{(Eq. 20)}$$

The expressions proposed for the reloading curves of bamboo under the cyclic uniaxial compressive loading regime are given in equations (21) and (22) that follow.

$$\sigma = \begin{cases} \alpha_1 \sigma_{un,(n+1)} (\bar{\epsilon})^{\eta_1} & 0 \leq \bar{\epsilon} < \bar{\epsilon}_1 \\ E_{pl} (\epsilon - \epsilon_{un,(n+1)}) + \sigma_{un,(n+1)} & \bar{\epsilon}_1 \leq \bar{\epsilon} \leq 1 \end{cases} \quad \text{(Eq. 21)}$$

$$E_{pl} = \frac{(\sigma_{un,(n+1)} - \alpha_2 \sigma_{un,n})}{(\alpha_3 (\epsilon_{un,(n+1)} - \epsilon_{pl;n}))} \quad \text{(Eq. 22)}$$

7. Results

The results are presented in the form of graphs, which include graphs from the experimental data and those from the proposed models. Several tables containing the data used were produced.

Figure 2: T1 Middle without node, Sample air dried

Figure 5: Measured and calculated data for the Reloading Curves (T1 Middle without node)

Figure 3: Measured and calculated data compared (T1 Middle without node)

Figure 6: Measured and Calculated data compared (T1 Middle without node)

Figure 4 : Measured and calculated data for the Unloading Curves (T1 Middle without node)

7.1. Tests Results

Figure 2 is the stress-strain diagram from the tests results of a sample of bamboo that was tested.

7.2. Envelope Curves:

Figures 3 represents the envelope curves obtained from the models proposed with those obtained from the experimental data. Each figure has four superposed graphs which are titled Measured, Fozao et al. 1, Fozao et al. 2 and Fozao et al. 3.

It can be observed from the diagrams above that the results from the proposed mathematical models fit closely well with the test results except in some few cases where there are some minor deviations.

7.3. Unloading Paths

Figures 4a to 4c below represent graphs of the

unloading paths from the test data and from the proposed models.

7.4. Reloading Curves

Figure 5 below represents the reloading curves from the test results and those obtained from the mathematical models. It will be seen from these diagrams that each reloading path has two curves superposed.

7.5. Cyclic Stress-Strain Curves

Figures 6a to 6c show the measured and calculated unloading and reloading paths of a sample of *Oxytenantera abyssinica* under cyclic uniaxial compressive loading. These curves are combined together to show a comparison of the experimental data and the data obtained from the proposed models for the cyclic behaviour of bamboo.

8. Discussion

8.1. Plastic Strain Behaviour of Bamboo

From the stress-strain diagrams plotted above, it can be seen that bamboo exhibits plastic behaviour. A hysteretic behaviour, characterized by non-overlapping unloading-reloading curves is also observed from these diagrams. Permanent residual strains are produced in the material beyond the proportional limit after the loads are removed producing a non linear behaviour.

It is observed from the unloading-reloading cycles

that at the end of each cycle, the residual or plastic strain increases as the number of cycles increase

Bamboo contains a large number of micro cracks even before any load is applied to it. This property is very decisive for the mechanical behavior of the material. The nonlinear behavior and the s-shape stress-strain curves of bamboo under uniaxial compressive stress can be associated with the micro-cracks propagation during load and stress-induced plastic flow in the specimen.

8.2. Comparison of Test Results with Proposed Models

From the stress-strain diagrams plotted above, it is observed that the overall stress-strain behaviour of the proposed models and tests results show similar configuration to each other as well as fit very well with each other.

It was observed that the samples soaked in water underwent several cycles before complete failure; meanwhile the samples tested after drying in an oven were very brittle. Though the dried samples had very high resistance than those soaked in water, their failure was very abrupt.

8.3. Perspectives for the Future

The future in the construction industry will be found in the use of bamboo and bamboo products. If adequate research is carried out to improve on the quality of this material and its products, then it can be used very effectively as a good construction material. The following are some areas that have been suggested for further research.

- i. Bamboo fiber reinforced plastics and composites.
- ii. Characterization of the bamboo species found in the Congo Basin Rain Forest.
- iii. Behaviour of bamboo under various tensile loading regimes.
- iv. Behaviour of bamboo under tri-axial compression and other compression loading regimes.
- v. Behaviour of bamboo fibers under tensile loads.
- vi. Behaviour of bamboo poles under dynamic loadings.

9. General Conclusion

Based on the present experimental investigations and the theoretical studies of the behaviour of bamboo under monotonic and cyclic uniaxial compressive loads, it can be concluded that:

- a. The behaviour of bamboo under these loads is nonlinear and this nonlinear behaviour can be modeled using the principles of endochronic theory of plasticity coupled with isotropic damage
- b. Bamboo possesses an envelope curve. This envelope curve may be considered to be unique and identical to the stress-strain curve obtained from a monotonic increasing uniaxial compressive loading.
- c. Bamboo possesses a shakedown limit such that, stresses above this limit will lead to additional strains, whereas maximum stresses at or below this limit will cause the stress strain history to go into a loop repeating the previous cycle without further permanent strain. This limit is the locus of points where the reloading portion of any cycle crosses the unloading portion.
- d. Most of the input data required for the models are obtained from laboratory tests results.
- e. When compared with the tests results, the mathematical models proposed show satisfactory agreement with the experimental results.

Keywords: *Constitutive modeling, uniaxial compressive loading, bamboo culms, endochronic theory of plasticity, isotropic damage.*

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